

Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD): An Evaluative Tool for Language Learning and Social Development in Early Childhood Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 13, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : ZPD, Early Childhood Education, Sociocultural theory, Story-telling, Play</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4940172</p>	<p><i>The focus of this research is the role of the concept of the Vygotsky's zone of proximal development (ZPD) in early childhood education. It highlights how this approach is helpful in the evaluation and assessment of mental and social development of children. The concept of ZPD alludes to cognitive functioning of children and their development that precedes from interaction with more capable and competent others, the competent adults (teachers) who take the initiative to impart education through guidance and encouragement in problem solving settings and adapt their level of help according to the requirement of the children and motivate them by placing in a challenging situation above their level to make them reach a level beyond the current zone, by exercising their full potential. With this concept of ZPD, the method of participant observation and conversation analysis has been used to study the eight selected 6-year old children who were stimulated with story-telling and observed for the roles they pick to play and the vocabulary usage. The study concludes that story-telling opens up the avenues for the children to go beyond their actual level of development and learn the language in a better manner through the acquisition of new words and try to use these words in their play and reach ZPD.</i></p>

Introduction

The *zone of proximal development* highlights the area which is between a child's current development, as a result of independently solving problems, and the extent of development- as appraised by problem solving under the guidance of an adult. ZPD offers a strategy to evaluate the internal mental development of the children. In this way, it is the domain between what the children currently understand and comprehend and what they have the potential to learn with guidance and assistance (Schaffer, 2009). ZPD uses scaffolding to stimulate the child to better perceive the world around them. Bruner (1996) has coined the term scaffolding for the assistance provided to push the child. In scaffolding, the adult does not simplify the task; however the learner's role is made simple "through the graduated intervention of the teacher" (Greenfield, 1984, p.119). For instance, three pennies, which stands for three sounds in 'man,' might be shown to a child and they are asked to put each penny on the table to express each sound in the word. The child might, finally, identify the sounds of words, without pennies. When the idea of making three sounds with placing three pennies is connected by the adult, they provide a scaffold to the child to progress from assisted to unassisted performance of task (Gellert & Elbro, 2017).

Related to classroom teaching is Vygotsky's idea of the role of play. According to it, the teacher needs to supply children, especially young, with many opportunities to play. The conceptual abilities of a child are sketched through play and imagination. Vygotsky argues that development is led by play. Vygotsky's concepts brought revolution in the field of learning, especially combining thought and language with socialization, he made learning a dynamic process involving the development of human higher mental function.

The degree of current development in this zone determines the actual development and perception for tomorrow. Education that does not exceed the current level of development becomes ineffective and incapable of achieving the potential level of development. ZPD at early stages pushes the children to go beyond their phase of learning, to step into what they are capable of learning with scaffolding. Vygotsky's wisdom becomes apparent in the notion of ZPD as it prompts them to accept the challenges and expand their learning horizons. Hence, learning, from this standpoint, is not a development merely, but a systematized process to enhance development.

The article employs ZPD as a mechanism for evaluation and judgment to determine children's level in the group with the help of story-telling techniques to increase the language proficiency of the child as their vocabulary is enhanced. Further the children use the vocabulary in the play practically. Egan (1997) perceives that the major tools, of young children, for understanding world and projecting their sense of it are poetic:

“This poetic world – emotional, imaginative, and metaphoric – is the foundation of our cultural life, as a species and individually. Logico-mathematical forms of thinking, or rationality, do not properly displace the poetic world, but rather grow out of and develop along with it; *they* are among *its* implications. The language and lore, fantasy narratives, metaphoric play, and games of young children constitute an oral culture that persists from generation to generation, sustained by the techniques of the poetic imagination and the psychological capacities evoked, stimulated, and developed initially by the need to remember and increasingly by the satisfaction the enlargement of our power over language gives us” (p. 69).

Even within a group that is created at an early level, all the children do not show the same degree of comprehension and learning. Their intellectual development does not correspond to the same age factor. Vocabulary enhancement through storytelling determines how the zone of proximal development helps the children by speeding up their process of learning and enhancing their intellectual development. For this reason the focus of this study is premises of mental and social development of individual children in a group. It tries to analyze the growth of children possessing various degrees of intellect and the acceleration in their social and cognitive abilities caused by the effective tools of scaffolding by determining their *ZPD*. Moreover, it helps to assess children at the early stages and prevents the barriers in their way to the acquisition of knowledge and the scaffolding through story-telling and play paves the process of language learning and social development. We argue that through proper evaluation and guidance, children struggling with educational and social development can be detected and early interference can pave the way to their better mental growth.

Assessment through Story-telling and Play

The technique of assessment and evaluation through story-telling and play is meaningful in educational settings at an early level of education as story-telling opens up the avenues for the children to go beyond their actual level of development and learn the language in a better manner through the acquisition of new words and try to use the words in their play. An effective mode, according to Haven (2007), of narration and instruction is storytelling. It creates a big difference in learning for children. Haven, in his famous book *Story Proof: The Science Behind the Startling Power of Story* cites Huttenlocher, a distinguished neurologist, whose research explored that brain of a human has been hardwired in such a way that it thinks and perceives in the terms of story (2007, p.26). It helps to examine the behaviour in a social context and helps to determine the mental level of the children in social and cultural milieu. Children listen to a story and the details imprint its effect by creating mental pictures and images thus facilitating deep understanding and perception as well as long lasting memory, more readily, than the abstract principles and set of facts (Tannen, 1989). Story-telling and play act as a tool to perceive the world of the children by incorporating their learning into some activity. The assessment of language proficiency through vocabulary enhancement during play helps to observe the children in real situations where they have the authority to control the circumstances, making or breaking the rules made by them using their own logic and understanding of the social context in which they are placed.

1. Children, with the help of play, are capable to not only master but also manage their life; or at least the portion of their life that the play forms (Garvey, 1977; 1990; Paley, 1992; 1997; 2001;2004; Corsaro, 1997; 2003).
2. It is their first independent activity system, which they consider as their own (Hakkarainen, 1990; 1999).
3. It is a holistic, aesthetic and creative archetype activity which helps in developing other kinds of creativity.

Simultaneously, a play is a source and mode of development as it creates the *ZPD* (Vygotsky, 1978; 1997).

Modern theories of play are founded on ‘*General Psychological Theories*’ such as ‘*Cognitive-Constructive Theories*’ (Piaget), ‘*Psychoanalytic Theories*’ (Freud, Erikson), ‘*Interaction Theories*’ (Mead), ‘*Cultural-Historical Theories*’ (Vygotsky, 1978), and ‘*Communication Theories*’ (Bateson). An interesting and unique effort to analyze a play is to ponder on improvisation in play interaction (Campbell & Sawyer, 2007). Some fundamental visible features of a play are agreed upon by several researchers. Hence, a play, for many, is flexible, joyful, intrinsically motivated and imaginative (Saracho & Spodek, 1998). The major concern, quite often, in definitions is “what is play and how to separate it from other types of behavior”. Definitions help in drawing limits and focusing on the framework of what to study.

Hughes (1999) provides an excellent example of this kind of frame: “Play has five essential characteristics. It is intrinsically motivated, freely chosen, pleasurable, non-literal, and actively engaged in by participants. Early theories of play emphasized its biological and genetic elements ... while contemporary theories stress the emotional, intellectual, and social benefits of play”(p. 25). Donald’s ‘*evolution of human consciousness theory*’ (2001) also explored the mental development taking place at the early of childhood. The interview study around sixteen countries of the world (Singer & Moscovici, 2008) exhibited that from the lives of children imaginative play has disappeared.

Reason and intellect are distinguished features of human beings which they possess in a unique way as compared with the animals. Each human being has varied levels of intellectuality, which includes the capability of understanding, vision, memorizing and classifying, thinking and reasoning, problem solving, theorizing,

conceptualizing and planning. All these qualities open up the range of possibilities. All this is the outcome of knowledge and education that enhances the cognition of the children and fosters their intellectual growth.

Early childhood education is a foundational phase for the child's, social, educational and cognitive competence in the future. It is essential to provide them with proper guidance and assistance not to make them passive but to accelerate their development. The proposition is that by integrating the *ZPD* and scaffolding into the system of education, the social and cognitive development of the children can be enhanced at early stages. Egan (1986; 1988; 1991; 1997 1999; 2005) has stressed the role of imagination in learning and advocated a different kind of educational interaction by the use of storytelling (teaching as storytelling) as the didactic dimension of the curriculum. In the same vein, Lindqvist (1995) proposed the idea of play words-the collaborative narrative venture of the adults and children as a developmental and progressive niche founded on play aesthetics. Moreover, the *ZPD* approach would enable us to perceive the individual differences of children in a group so that better strategies could be adopted to cope with the situation. Involvement and engagement of teachers and elders in the group of children through scaffolding would help them to perceive the situation from their point of view. It would be helpful in the mental and social cognition and the growth of the children at early childhood stage. Haven (2007) further adds, "stories struggle to infiltrate the normal flow of education" (p.4). The evaluation method of *ZPD* equips the teachers with an insight into the real potential of the children enabling them to plan adequately for the future. *ZPD* technique is beneficial at the early childhood stage as it is also practical in multicultural settings and helps to deal with children of varying capabilities coming from diverse backgrounds and different age groups. Zone of proximal development through scaffolding provides an opportunity for the teachers to get close to the children without disturbing their natural behaviour and workings.

Children like playing and it is the domain where the zone of proximal development can be determined more effectively. Six separate stages of play are described by Parten (1932). These stages focus on social and developmental aspects of the activity:

- Unoccupied (play)
- Solitary (independent) play
- Onlooker play (behaviour)
- Parallel play (adjacent play, social coaction)
- Associative play
- Cooperative play

The principles and rules of instructional formation as well as guidance of creative play activity, in early childhood pedagogy, were developed (Usova, 1976). Children imitate their elders and want to be engaged in play. The play reveals the hidden aspects of the personality of children and opens up avenues to raise their level of perception in problem solving.

A binary relation is allowed between, by *ZPD*, the learner and 'the more competent other' in the social context. In *ZPD*, relation between the child and the competent other is produced endogenously, in collaboration with each other. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the socio- cognitive development of children. Moreover, it aims to explore how the zone of proximal development can act as an effective tool to determine the higher mental functions. To achieve these objectives, this study explores the effects of story-telling and play in early childhood for reaching the *ZPD*. In order to achieve this the study poses following questions:

Q1- How does the zone of proximal development assess the cognitive as well as the social development of the children through story-telling technique?

Q2-How does scaffolding work within the ambit of the zone of proximal development to assess and evaluate the development and learning of the children?

Research Methodology

Assessment and evaluation are the constituents of everyday life. Observation is the essence of assessment as it focuses on the situation and notices certain characteristics (Das 1994). To assess and evaluate the potential level of social and cognitive development of children, the method of observation and conversation analysis has been used, while the children were engaged in playing and other activities through scaffolding. In the past, observation was not considered to be an important method (Wass & Golding, 2014). But with the passage of time, it has gained currency and it has been realized that observation provides first-hand knowledge of the real situations through the sensory organs. It is however essential to discriminate between observation- as a qualitative data collection- and participant observation. The latter is characterized by supremacy of immersion and interaction in a specific setting and environment unlike simple observation which is not site specific and can be employed randomly even in interviews (Padgett, 2008).

The focus is on unaccountable qualities of human being's social skills, interactions and communication. That's why observation has been integrated with conversation analysis. For the present study participant observation has been selected as it is different from systematic observation that focuses just on measuring and recording the event, its length and duration (Denscombe , 2014). Participant observation allows not only close observation but also allows an opportunity for the observer to become a part of the situation. It also gives a chance to dig a little deep in case there is the need for further explanation. This is ensured by taking the school

authorities as well as teachers in confidence. In this kind of participatory observation, the maintenance of consistent behaviour is essential as it is how children gain confidence.

Conversation analysis is an important method of assessment as conversation is a significant structured activity as explained by Egan (2005). Turn at talk emphasizes how the conversation is modeled and structured. Turn taking is an important feature of conversation: speakers and listeners exchange their roles and positions in order to start the speech (Coulthard, 2011). The turn taking is not random and is distributed among the speakers but in case of the present study the conversation taking place among children is not controlled as the purpose is to analyze their mental and social development. Conversation analysis of the talk of children throws light on the way they think and behave as well as the mode in which they interact.

Sampling

The present study employs a strategic sampling method to select the sample group from the population. This particular method is selected as it enables the sample on the basis of a certain criteria. In the present case, the population is not a large number. It consists of only eight children from class prep who come to the PAF Montessori at 8am and spend their day there till 1pm. The children have been selected on the basis of age. All the children were six years old.

Method of Data collection

The research was conducted in PAF Montessori Islamabad. Eight children from the same class were selected for observation and the analysis of their speech was also done. It was made sure that all the children were of the same age having the supervision of the same teacher although it is not possible to control their backgrounds. Before starting the research, a letter of consent from the parents as well as school administration was obtained. The names of the school children were not used in the research operation and findings. The information was gathered through first-hand participant observation and it was noted down. No audio visual recording was used. The data was written on the observation sheets. The participant observation lasted for five working school days in which every day a separate sheet was used for the collection of data.

The purpose of the observation with this group of eight children was to observe their interaction during their play time as well as to gather the chunks of their speech where they had used vocabulary items earlier listened to through story-telling in the class. It was keenly observed that children at an early stage share roles making the rules of the game and use different strategies to keep the game peaceful. The participant observation was first hand as time was spent with the children, playing with them the way they played by becoming a part of their environment. During this process, conversation was made with them to understand their motivations and explanations. In the start children were curious at the presence of an adult other than their teacher but soon they were comfortable and behaved naturally. In qualitative analysis and research the unalienable part of the researcher is significant. But at the same time, objectivity is maintained by excluding the input of personal feelings. The present research carries on the Narrative Method which is descriptive analysis of the situation of observation.

Findings

Findings were concluded on the basis of observation and analysis of conversation of children where they had used the new vocabulary items. The roles that the children picked during their play raised certain questions related to the development of the children. The aim of choosing role play was to observe children during play that how they made the social rules and interact in that social environment. During the class session, while phonics were being taught to the students through audio visual aids, the girl A from the selected group stood and said; "I am the teacher's helper ya? Don't speak! Shhhhhhh....we won't be able to learn if you speak".

The girl A herself picked up the role of teacher's helper out of her own sense of duty and judgment. She started monitoring other children. Other kids didn't accept her role and complained to the teacher who interfered to resolve the situation. Girl A stated that she didn't learn things when there was noise. So she thought of assuming the role of teacher's helper to curb the disturbance. In the realm of playing the girl reached the zone of proximal development that helped to reveal the potential and also highlighted the hurdle in the way of learning. It was not possible to reach ZPD in other situations. It is especially helpful in the case of children who do not talk a lot and are shy. Fifth dimension, a learning atmosphere for motivation and sense making was invented by Cole (1996). Playing a role leads the child to the *zone of proximal development* with the help of activities. Children play various roles from major domains like animals, family and professions. While playing with animals, they assume the character of an animal or sometimes they take the role of a teacher, a doctor or a pilot etc. when playing the role they step into that state and act in accordance with the specific behaviour. They think differently, accept the responsibilities, reflect logically and present arguments. The role play is not arbitrary but mentally planned by the child, and the rules of the play are made to keep the play going peacefully. Rules lie at the center of the play.

In the classroom the children were asked about certain vocabulary items and it was ascertained that they didn't know the meaning and use of those words. After this a story was narrated keeping their age in mind. The children were amused to listen to the story and afterwards the children of the sample group were observed. It was discovered that the children picked up certain words from the story that they didn't know and employed it

in the play and conversation. Thus it was analyzed that with the help of the technique of story telling the children were able to land in the *zone of proximal development* and gained proficiency in language use by acquiring new vocabulary items. Children were seated in a circle and the following story of the brave lion was told to them:

“The brave lion lived in the forest with his family. The forest was full of wild animals. There were lakes and ponds all around. The cubs of the lion were mischievous and didn’t follow the instructions of their father. The lion asked them not to go into the deep and dense jungle where there was pitch dark. He wanted to protect from danger. The cubs didn’t listen to their father and went to the dense part of the forest. A huge monster gripped them strongly and put them in the cage. They wept and screamed until the lion came for their rescue. They promised never to disobey their father in the future.”

The meanings of the new words were explained to the children by the researcher. Afterwards they were given a break. The children of the sample group were observed. It was discovered that two children from the selected sample were sitting on the carpet, and they treated the carpet as the parking lot, assuming themselves as the parents coming to take their children from the school. The conversation they made revealed that they were making use of the vocabulary items picked from the story in the class.

G1: I have come to pick my daughter from school. She is very mischievous.

G: 2 My son studies in the school. He too is wild.

G1: Children don’t listen to their parents.

G2: we just want to protect them from danger.

G1: My daughter always promises to listen to what I say but don’t listen in the end

G2: children are involved with mobiles all the time and don’t listen to us.

It was discovered from this conversation between two kids who were playing and imitating their parents who had come to pick them from the school that kids were using different new words from the story narrated in the classroom. They learnt these new words through the playful activity of story-telling and used them in the activity they themselves created for playing. The children used five new words picked and learnt from the story.

The other kids were also discovered using the words they learned from the story. It was a fun activity for them to use these new words and incorporate them in their talk. It was also discovered that those kids who learned more words took the more turns in the talk. The two other kids from the sample group used new vocabulary items.

G3: I want to be a cat.

B4: you have to be a dog.

G3: No, I want to be a cat because they are wild and playful.

B4: No, you can’t be a cat. They are dangerous.

B4: They are like monsters. I would like to put them in the cage.

G3: They are cute. Don’t put them in the cage.

B4: you can’t be cat as you already have a cat at your home. You will have to be a dog as they are brave.

The conversation is reflective of the behaviour of the children. It is clear that children’s development was improved and they made progress in language proficiency by not only acquiring new vocabulary items but also by practicing them in the playful conversation. Story-telling helped them to go beyond their realm of current development when they didn’t know certain vocabulary items. It helped to make the children land in the zone of proximal development where they exercised their potential by learning and using new words of vocabulary thus enhancing their language proficiency. When they are independent, they accept the responsibilities and act out of the normal frame. They become more logical out of necessity and step out of the current zone of development into the proximal zone of development; they need to enhance their faculties. They use peaceful language avoiding any harsh or bad words. They behave more sensibly. Even the boy who learned more vocabulary items was enthusiastic to use them in the play field and he took turns during the talk. Play, at school stage, is majorly observed as a tool for achieving academic goals of learning as it is evident from the terms such as ‘*playful learning*’, ‘*play based learning*’, or ‘*guided learning*’ Fisher, Hirsh-Pasek, Golinkoff, Berk, & Singer, 2010). We found that the play’s didactic dimensions are unlimited as it is an activity which involves a child and becomes a reason for the most universal, the most fundamental meanings of human activity. The transition, according to Vygotsky (1978; 1997), from operational (concrete) to abstract and logical thinking (in concepts) are facilitated by playful activities.

Play is not just only a developmental contributor and children’s specific mode of acting it is also a tool to facilitate learning in accordance with age. Observation revealed that the play does not intercept the realistic nature of learning but facilitates it. Play opens up the realm of possibilities and allows the children to land in the zone of proximal development. Vygotsky (1997) emphasized that from the standpoint of development, a play accommodates changes in consciousness as well as needs more adequately than simply learning through academics. The analysis reveals that different forms and kinds of oral plays have had a positive and unique impact on the children’s social and language development.

According to *Sociocultural Theory*, in the development of a child's 'consciousness,' 'personality' and his/her 'relationship with reality,' the social environment has a major role (Vygotsky, 1997). When Vygotsky talks about the development of a child's personality, he is actually stressing specifically human characteristics and higher psychological functions which are stimulated only by the social environment.

Another conversation analysis of three children from the sample group was done. One of them was upset and was not playing while the others were trying to negotiate.

B5: Why are you not playing anymore?

B6: Because..... (Calling the name of a girl and pointing at her) took the toy from my hand.

B5: why are you weeping?

B6: Nothing (showing unhappy face)

B5: You know you have to tell your friends if someone teases you or says something that you don't like.

B6: Ok (nodding the head)...

G7: No, the girls are not wild like this. It's always the boys who tease us first.

B5: why don't you go to that girl and tell her to give back the toy and don't be a monster as it was in your hand and if she does not, we will go together.

B6: Ok (nodding the head).....

G7: No, she must be asked politely .She will follow

G7: Boys are always harsh. They are not brave like cubs.

B5: No, the girls must behave well. My sister does the same at home.

B5: Boys always protect their sisters because they are huge.

B6: I am a brave cub. (Goes to the girl and gets the toy back. He comes back with a happy smile.

The conversation between three kids again reflects that they learned new vocabulary items from the narrative story and used them in their talk as they improved their vocabulary and felt good to express it in their use of language. On closely observing the pattern of the conversation it is observed that children especially girls are basically cooperative in nature. B5 asks B6 to go to the girl and ask for the toy harshly but G7 argues against it. She intervenes in the matter to resolve the situation. B5 and G7 take the turns at two places as they know more vocabulary items as compared with B6 who used only one new word. She blames the boys for being rude and stubborn while B5 says that girls always create fuss as his sister does the same at home. B5 sees the logic from the angle of his small social world and he is at the same time ready to help B2. The conversation among the children allows them to open up their hearts and minds and in doing so they get close to the *ZPD*. At the end the resolution of the situation amicably also hints at the problem solving ability of the children who take responsibility and make decisions when confronted with a critical situation.

In another observation, B8 from the sample group was found to be sitting alone. When he was asked the reason of his not joining other children, he said;

B3: They don't want to play with me. They think I am mischievous.

R: Did they tell you that?

B3: No, but one of them was telling the other that he wants to play with him.

R: So he didn't say that he does not want to play with you.

B3: No. But they think I don't follow them.

R: Why don't you go and tell him that you also want to play with him.

B3: O...k (hesitant and confused).

This child B8 also showed improvement in his language proficiency as he also made use of the new vocabulary items he didn't know earlier. His current development reached the level of potential development in learning new vocabulary items and integrating them in his conversation. The children try to resolve their problems and issues through negotiation and verbal interaction. It represents their desire of not wanting to lose their friends.

Discussion

In the above research findings, it is reflected that children exercise their own specific reason and commonsense and they have their own unique logic. Such logic is activated while playing or performing different activities. In this situation, the child actually enters the *zone of proximal development* that is responsible for higher mental functioning.

The present research revolves around the notion of a *zone of proximal development*. It not only develops social skills but also enhances the logic and cognitive faculties. *ZPD* helps in achieving the potential level of development through play. Children at play are mostly at their *ZPD* rather than at their actual zone of development. In formal settings of education *ZPD* is not visible; it reaches its climax while children show their potentialities to the fullest while playing. Role playing serves as an effective mode to observe the children from a unique angle, where they reach the level of proximal development as they imitate the social role plays and try to perform them by going beyond their mental horizons and exert their full energies to utilize their potential. According to Vygotsky, play enables the thought to be detached from objects. Action takes place with the help

of thoughts not with objects (Cole, 1978). It was also discovered that those kids who learned more words took the more turns in the talk.

When the children are placed in a role play situation, they try to imitate the elders by acting more reasonably and judiciously as the elder would have acted in the same situation so he tries to think beyond his normal pattern of thinking and here the potential level is attained to the fullest. When he is acting as a leader, he tries to put on the shoes of a leader and act accordingly. Similarly in the position of father, the children try to imitate perfectly how they want to see the father and sometimes even try to cover the flaws that they do not want to see in their own fathers. The children use their imagination to assume what seems best and reaches their higher mental functioning. Our study thus favours the opinion of Egan (1999) that childhood is a stage of the development of human mental faculties and potentials, opening up the possibilities for future growth. A child, with the help of adequate support and guidance, reaches the creative potential of culture. To comprehend the real essence of a phenomenon or an object, the child imagines it, grasps it -to translate it into an image- and tries to perceive it from potential perspectives in order to explore its real nature (Davydov, 1996). Hence, in this way, the world is perceived by a child from an unconventional perspective. This phenomenon is termed, by Chukovsky (1974), as 'inversions' or 'topsy turvies'. They are also declared as 'mental games' or 'thinking games' by him. According to Vygotsky this imaginative play stimulates the highest mental functions of the child and leads him to better understanding by widening his zone of proximal development. Egan (1999) elaborated: "children's thinking is not merely some embryonic and simple form of adults' thinking but has distinctive characteristics of its own – some of which are clearly superior to typical adults' thinking" (p. 29). We conclude that a child's imagination can be enhanced in a formal education setting by using storytelling and opportunities to play.

Recent research in the systemic psychophysiology domain (Diamond, Barnett, Thomas & Munro, 2007) provides testimony that along with behavioral aspects, the human brain's architecture is also affected by societal and cultural modes of life. Using Vygotsky's (1978) proposal that a play facilitates and develops a zone of *proximal development*, our study finds the effectiveness of role-play in children's linguistic and social development.

The research further helped to analyze that the zone of *proximal development* (*ZPD*) serves as an effective tool of assessment and evaluation. This is stimulated, in our study, with the help of these two mentioned techniques. They help children not only to come out of the present zone but also to reach *ZPD*. In the present research, the story telling technique improved the vocabulary of the children and they learned the things they didn't know earlier. It determined the social and cognitive development of children which is not considered in the traditional classroom educational instruction. Our research highlights the importance of using storytelling in the classroom; and favours Lockett and Jones (2009) who say; "Story-telling should serve as a major component in an elementary curriculum" (p. 177). Furthermore, our study emphasizes the implications of Vygotsky's '*Sociocultural Theory*' for child development in early years, since it focuses on social interaction's role in the development of higher mental faculties. Socio cultural milieu helps to reach the zone of proximal development through play. Vygotsky claims that, "we need to concentrate not on the product of development but on the very process by which higher forms are established" (Vygotsky, 1978, 64). The child in the natural play acts spontaneously to a certain situation and that determines the efficacy of his higher mental functions. Our study supports Vygotsky's claim that human higher mental functions originating on the social plane brought revolution in the field of education as it redefines the role of imaginative and role play activities, peer and peer interaction in the process of development.

Conclusion

Early education of the child is of utmost importance in developing his higher mental and cognitive functions and once this phase of development is ignored and repressed, there is no remedy. In a way education and mechanism of schools provide a valuable insight into the social thinking regarding the realms of thought and intellect. It has been observed that the majority of teachers are unaware of Vygotsky's concept of the *zone of proximal development* (*ZPD*) and are unable to use it for the purpose of assessment and evaluation. Similarly the concept of scaffolding and role playing to enhance the socio-cognitive faculties of the children is not widespread in early year school education. The study reveals that the children's conversation, while playing, allows them to open up their hearts and minds and in doing so they get close to the *ZPD*. There is a need to create awareness regarding the work of Vygotsky to revolutionize the domains of child development and pedagogy through teacher training sessions. It is of significant importance to focus also on the *zone of proximal development* in the broad multicultural spectrum of education where social development and language learning flourish with storytelling and play.

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